

FORMATION AND DEVELOPMENT OF PERSONALITY'S WILL QUALITIES IN ADOLESCENTS

Preobrazhensky Ilya Stanislavovich

Student of the Faculty of Sports Activities and Management

Termez State University

Annotation: The question of the relevance of the formation of volitional qualities in modern adolescents leaves no doubt. The author claims that this is due to the advent of gadgets. But in the course of the analysis it was found out that there are more factors influencing the volitional qualities of a teenager. In order to neutralize the causes, the article formed a number of recommendations.

Key words: teenager, gadgets, developmental psychology, volitional qualities, formation and development.

Introduction. For modern society, the social development of a teenager is important. He needs skills such as conflict resolution, overcoming difficulties, endurance, justice, perseverance, the desire for self-development [1, 2, 3]. However, more and more often, when performing a task, you can hear from a teenager that he does not want to do it or will not. At the same time, the teenager does not explain the reason for this behavior. Thus, showing a weak development of volitional qualities or their complete absence [4, 5].

This problem has become relevant in modern society with the advent of gadgets, virtual games and social networks, free access to the Internet [6, 7]. All this is more and more absorbing the free time from school and the attention of adolescents. The time spent in this way does not carry a positive benefit for the development of his volitional qualities [8, 9]. On the contrary, they are even more "blunted". This is due to the fact that in virtual reality these qualities are not used and do not develop. Moreover, in reality, it becomes harder for a teenager to force himself to do something.

Volitional qualities are characterized by the manifestation of human activity [10, 11]. Human activity is understood as a conscious and selective action of a person, aimed at transforming the surrounding space and the person himself [12, 13, 14]. For example, activity in various spheres of life: work, educational activities, communication.

According to D. Y. Turdimuradov, volitional qualities are the presence of consciously set goals, motivation in achieving the goal and overcoming obstacles on the way to this goal [15, 16]. In Russian psychology, volitional qualities are equated with character traits. So, in the works of some researchers, character is presented as the basis of will, where the totality of the most essential and stable features of human behavior reflect the originality of his volitional qualities [17, 18].

So, the analysis of scientific literature allows us to conclude that the volitional activity of a teenager is a complex formation, which includes such components as dynamic (a physiological mechanism that allows a person to control his behavior), content (determines the direction of the will) and social and personal (reflects the ability to apply the formed volitional properties in the process of implementing volitional activity) [19, 20].

The following factors contribute to the formation of volitional qualities of a teenager:

- 1) Thoughtful mode and daily routine. A child, accustomed from childhood to a certain regimen, knows how to correctly allocate his time.
- 2) Mastering new knowledge and skills at school and at home. Following the teacher's instructions, as well as doing homework in a timely manner, is an indicator that the child is mastering his discipline.
- 3) A variety of means, forms and methods of conducting training sessions. Thanks to the universal method of conducting educational activities, the child gets the opportunity to develop comprehensively, thereby laying the foundation for further purposefulness.
- 4) Physical culture and sports. Playing sports helps to improve in terms of strengthening not only health, but also the training of volitional qualities.

- 5) A unified approach on the part of parents. The support of parents is a support in the improvement of volitional qualities.
- 6) Personal example of adults. For example, a courageous and courageous act on the part of adults may become a goal that a teenager wants to achieve.
- 7) Using the effect of rivalry. In the course of the "competition", the teenager receives motivation to achieve his goal.

Conclusions. Based on these factors, it is possible to form a set of rules and recommendations that will help to form strong-willed qualities in adolescents. These recommendations are suitable for use by both adults (parents, teachers) and the teenager himself. Thus, for the formation of volitional qualities, it is necessary to take the following measures:

1. Involvement in socially useful activities, taking into account the interests of a teenager. But at the same time, it is necessary to give significance to the task assigned not only for the performing teenager, but also for the entire team in which he is located.
2. Initiative in socially useful affairs. This measure is much more productive than the first. Here the teenager himself must show a desire to do something for the team in which he is, that is, take responsibility.
3. Strengthening faith in one's own strength. In order for a teenager to be involved in social activities and even more so to take the initiative, the support of adults and surrounding peers is necessary.
4. Persuasion, encouragement, approval, tact and trust - these methods should be used with a teenager. Only in such ways is it possible to show self-confidence in a teenager.
5. For violation use the public opinion of the environment. A teenager should feel responsible when performing a particular task. Thus, adolescence is the most difficult and complex of all childhood ages. It has to do with personality development. The formation of volitional qualities in adolescents is expressed in the following: from the ability to manage oneself, concentrate efforts, withstand and endure heavy loads to the ability to manage activities and achieve high results in it.

According to this logic, the methods of developing volitional qualities are being replaced and improved.

References:

1. Turdimurodov D.Y. Pedagogical factors of external stimulation affecting the volitional efforts of schoolchildren during physical exercises of a different nature / D.Y. Turdimurodov // *Innovations in pedagogy and psychology*. - 2020. - №. 9. Issue 3. - P. 21-25.
2. Turdimurodov Dilmurod Yuldashevich. (2022). Education and development of volitive qualities in schoolchildren by means of physical education. *Academicia Globe: Inderscience Research*, 3(01), 59–62.
3. Турдимуродов, Д. Й. (2021). Спорт ўйинлари билан шуғулланиш жараёнида ўқувчиларда иродавий сифатларнинг шаклланиш хусусиятлари. *Актуальные научные исследования в современном мире*, 3(9 (77)), 140-144.
4. Turdimurodov, D. (2022). Volitional qualities of a person and their formation in adolescent age. *Models and methods in modern science*, 1(14), 13-17.
5. Ёулдашев, Т. Д. (2022). Воспитание и развитие волевых качеств у школьников средствами физического воспитания. *Ижтимоий фанларда инновация онлайн илмий журнали*, 2(1), 204–207.
6. Turdimurodov, D. Y. (2021). Preschool period: pedagogical aspect of education of will in a child. *Current Research Journal of Pedagogics (2767-3278)*, 2(09), 47-51.
7. Turdimurodov, D. Y. (2021). Testing volitional qualities for students of high schools of secondary school. *The American Journal of Social Science and Education Innovations*, 3(03), 405-413.
8. Турдимуродов, Д. (2021). Formation and education of will in schoolchildren in the process of physical education lesson. *Mental Enlightenment Scientific-Methodological Journal*, 2021(02), 64-74.
9. Turdimurodov, D. Y. (2022, September). Formation of moral and volitional qualities of adolescents by means of physical education. In *International scientific*

conference "Innovative trends in science, practice and education" (Vol. 1, No. 1, pp. 198-204).

10. Turdimurodov Dilmurod Yuldoshevich. (2021). The formation of readiness for skilled tensions in the process of physical education. *Archive of Conferences*, 21-24.

11. Turdimurodov, D. Y. (2021). Willed qualities of a personality and ways of their formation in sport. *ISJ Theoretical & Applied Science*, 12 (104), 689-692.

12. Турдимуродов, Д. Ю. (2022). Влияние занятий единоборствами на уровень проявления морально - волевых качеств учащихся общеобразовательной школы. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 3(1), 691-698.

13. Yuldashevich, T. D. (2022). Application of Innovative Technologies in the Process of Formation of Will Qualities. *European Multidisciplinary Journal of Modern Science*, 4, 826–828.

14. Преображенский, И. С. (2022). Применение инновационных технологий в процессе формирования волевых качеств. *Barqarorlik va yetakchi tadqiqotlar onlayn ilmiy jurnali*, 2(3), 234-236.

15. Турдимуродов, Д. Ю. (2022). Формирование у подростков волевых качеств в процессе физического воспитания. *Science and Education*, 3(7), 283-289.

16. Турдимуродов Д. Й. Возможности средств физического воспитания в формировании волевых качеств у школьников / Д. Й. Турдимуродов. // *Инновации в педагогике и психологии*. -2021. - № 7. Выпуск 4. - С. 74-80

17. Turdimurodov, D. Y. (2021). Features of the manifestation of volitional efforts in the process of external stimulation in schoolchildren of 10-12 years old. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 2(4), 1348-1354.

18. Турдимуродов, Д. (2022). Жисмоний тарбия дарси мактаб ўқувчиларида иродавий сифатларни ривожлантирувчи восита сифатида. *Жамият ва инновациялар*, 3(6/S), 74–80.

19. Yuldashevich, T. D. (2022). Education of moral-volitional and psychological qualities in athletes. Problems and scientific solutions, Australia, Melbourne.

20. Турдимуродов, Д. (2022). Урок физического воспитания как средство развития волевых качеств у школьников. *Общество и инновации*, 3(6/S), 74–80.